

INTONATION FEATURES OF PARENTHETICAL CLAUSES IN ENGLISH

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Summary

This work is devoted to students' assimilation of English phrasal intonation. While working with foreign students, many teachers of English as a non-native language notice that often even advanced students do not fully master the English intonation. What can this be related to? It can be assumed that not enough time is given to intonation in classes on English as a foreign language. The basics of English intonation are learned by students at the first lessons, but there is usually no corrective intonation course for them. While studying a foreign language, the student faces prosodic interference, which is not always overcome properly. Often students transfer the intonation of their first language to the language being studied, and the success in mastering the intonation often depends on the "base" from which the student started learning English.

The widespread use of English as the global language of the world community is an irrefutable proof that today the English language occupies a special position in the framework of international communication, thus becoming a lingua franca. But even in the XIX century, English claimed only the position of an international language, being on a par with Spanish, French and other languages of communication adopted by the UN [8, p. 5]. The term lingua franca in this study is used based on the definition given to it by V.A. Chiribka. He claims that lingua franca is a language that is systematically used to create possible conditions for communication between speakers of different languages [1. T.12 p. 213].

The history of the formation of the English language is diverse and is caused by a number of historical factors. For many centuries, the development of the language was influenced by various phenomena, whether it was war or peaceful language contacts. But it is worth highlighting three main periods during which the English language experienced the most significant changes. One of these periods is the Early Middle Ages, which is characterized by a large influence of French and other languages, so, for example, the Anglo-Saxon language in the VIII century fell under the influence of the language of the Scandinavians. The Scandinavian influence not only affected the language's vocabulary, but also extended to morphology and syntax (the ending of the 3rd person singular "-s", the ending of "-and" participles (now "-ing")). The Scandinavian conquest was followed by the Norman, and the traces left by the French language in English can still be seen.

The second no less important period in the history of the English language is the Renaissance, the era of prosperity of the language, the beginning and development of literary creativity, the formation of the national literary language. As well as the third period, the period of modern English, the beginning of the new Millennium, the era of new trends in the development and popularization of the language. [2. T.1 p. 43]

The spread of the English language around the world began in the sixties of the XX-th century. English has ceased to be the language only of England and America, it has spread to a number of countries, such as India, Canada, Australia and many others.

But why did English get the right to take the position of the language of international communication? D. Krystal notes that this choice is not related to the number of people who speak a particular language. For example, Latin was the international language of the Roman Empire, not because the Romans outnumbered the rest, but because they were a more powerful nation. Thus, we can conclude that the military power of a people who speak a particular language is one of the main reasons for its superiority. In addition, it should be noted that the structure of the language also does not affect the extent of its distribution. Of course, the English language in comparison with many others shows a lighter grammatical structure, lack of inflections and ordered syntax. But if we return to the Latin language again, and also recall the historical influence of such languages as French, Greek, and Spanish, we will confirm our conclusion that the criterion of ease of language acquisition is not a fundamental reason on the way to acquiring the status of an international language. [3. T.1 p. 350]

As mentioned earlier, military force is one of the main reasons for language dominance, but D. Krystal adds that the authority of an international language is also the result of the economic influence of the nation

that speaks it. This factor became important only at the beginning of the XX-th century, when the economy reached the global level, which was due to the development of radio communications and telecommunications. It was the United Kingdom at the beginning of the XIX century that established itself as a leader in trade and industry. By the end of the nineteenth century, the US economy had grown and gained momentum, becoming the most dynamic and productive in the world. Throughout the nineteenth century, British policy was aimed at spreading the English language to all countries of the world, and in the twentieth century it was joined by America: activity in international trade, initiative in the media, the development of advertising, cinema and mass entertainment. English owes its spread to the US dollar. [4. T.1 p. 18]

Today's growing interest in the study of samples of spoken speech needs to address the actual discourse of people of different origins, belonging to different social classes and entering into verbal interaction due to different communication situations, with specific pragmatic attitudes. Regardless of the fact that we live in the age of computer technology and technological progress, there are certain social processes and phenomena in which it is impossible or, at least, extremely difficult to replace with something live, human communication. Such processes include the educational process. In higher education, it is based on conducting classes, mainly in the form of lectures and seminars. An educational lecture is the main form of training at a University, and, among other points, the most important role in achieving the main purpose of the educational lecture is played by the teacher's speech culture, one of the most important components of which is pronunciation.

In the framework of modern linguistics was developed sociolinguistic model of functioning of the native language and speech, including the structure of interdependent components related to physiological and neuropsychiatric characteristics of individuals but also with the specifics of the formation of individual speech code is influenced by linguistic and extralinguistic factors. Thus, traces of the native language when operating in English or any foreign language are shown as an accent on the phonetic level of interlanguage interference.

A full-fledged study of a foreign accent involves both the use of observation data on the interfered English speech of foreigners (analysis from the position of the listener), and the diagnosis of the results of comparing the sound structure of the studied language with the native language of the speaker (analysis from the position of the speaker). In the course of working on this research, we conducted a phonetic and phonological analysis of real works of monological speech of non-native English speakers (non-native English speakers). The first stage of the study was the selection of material. The material for this study was audio / video recordings of speech of lecturers of higher educational institutions in Europe, who use English as a means of learning, posted in free access on the video hosting Youtube. Next, we identified phonetic features of the lecturers' speech in terms of interlanguage interference (the speaker's native language + English). It is worth noting that the origin of teachers and their native language play an important role in the process of identifying features of interaction between different language systems at the phonetic level. As a pronouncing norm of the English language, the British pronunciation standard (Received Pronunciation) was taken as the basis. At the end of the study, based on the data obtained, we identified phonetic characteristics inherent in all informants, and attributed them to the characteristics of the English language as a means of learning. [5. T.2 p. 12]

Let's consider the features of phonetic design of the speech of informants-native Spanish speakers. As the first sample of monologue speech, we selected video lectures by two teachers of European universities, the University of Groningen and the University of Granada (hereinafter, "Lecturer 1" and "Lecturer 2", respectively) with Spanish origin. [6. T.1 p. 70]

The scope of business correspondence, which is more commonly used at the international level, is constantly expanding. The communicative purpose of business correspondence is not limited to the communication of any data, it is important to use expressive means to arouse the reader's confidence and convince him to perform some action. In this context, certain formulas of expressiveness and expressiveness of representatives of different language cultures (in this case, native speakers of English and German) are of particular importance, since the systems of different languages have their own peculiarities of speech influence implementation.

In business texts, expressive elements have an impact on the emotional sphere of the addressee, and also allow the addressee to realize their own attitude to the described problem. In business correspondence, most often we are talking about material goods that encourage the interlocutors of the correspondence to obtain their own benefits. Thanks to emotionally-colored means, communicants Express their intentions in order to effectively implement a communicative goal. [7. T.9 p. 221]

When analyzing it, it is important to keep in mind that business letters are divided primarily by subject and communication purpose, for example: letters of inquiry, complaints, complaints, offers, etc. Some

linguists also pay attention to the separation of traditional business letters and letters that are sent via email. E-mails as more modern versions of correspondence with a more informal linguistic-stylistic structure are of particular interest in the study, so after analyzing traditional request letters, the impact of e-mail correspondence will be described at the end of the practical part.

The expressiveness of intonation using brackets in business correspondence can be considered at different levels of writing. Graphic and font text highlighting tools help the author of the letter not only emphasize a certain semantic part of the statement, but also contribute to a more understandable perception of the text and implicitly attract the reader's attention. In addition, it is important to emphasize the role of paragraphs in writing, which are used to Express the signals of the beginning and end of the thought, which provides a clear logic of the narrative. These structural elements make it easier for the recipient to perceive information.[8. T.12 p. 14]

Lexical means of expressiveness are aimed at implementing the communicative intentions of the interlocutors. Pragmatic attitudes determine the degree of their expressiveness. In the letters, the requests will be further described certain linguistic terms, which are highlighted in the work of the Y. M. Malinovich. We are talking about lexical (emotionally-colored words and expressions) and morphological (suffixes with an additional figurative meaning) means of expression that affect the recipient's subconscious. From the point of view of the topic-rematic division of the text, such means as repetition or parallelism emphasize important parts and distribute the updating of information in accordance with the communicative task. Label formulas for letter design at the beginning and end usually have a positive effect on the recipient. And the main part of the business text not only carries all the semantic load, but also is accompanied by a positive modality and assessment of the described issue. [9. T.6 p. 43]

Thus, the expressiveness of intonation using brackets can be manifested at the level of graphics, morphology, vocabulary, and syntax. In addition, it is worth emphasizing that the compositional components of the text influence the perception and further behavior of the recipient.

Request letters or requests are the most common type of business correspondence that represent more than just the initial intent at the beginning of the correspondence. Orders or requirements are most often passed already in the process of long-term cooperation. Requests are made in the framework of the need to obtain any relevant information that is important for performing operations in the business sphere. [10. T.1 p. 158]

These letters can be considered as motivations, because in correspondence, one interlocutor tries to persuade the partner to pass on certain data for further cooperation and mutual benefits. Moreover, the request expresses some illocutionary acts with the purpose of requiring that the desired information be forwarded.

Request letters have a common communicative purpose, which is characterized by a common desire to change the direction of the situation discussed in the correspondence. The author's intention arises from the desire to change the course of certain events in the business sphere by identifying new information for the previous state of Affairs. Therefore, the subject of the situation changes later and the desired communicative goal is realized at the end. Impulses are generated by using certain linguistic resources, which are reflected in the requests, orders, or requirements. In other words, this type of email can be viewed from the point of view of incentives for action, and partners – initiators of communication. Despite the fact that the status of the interlocutors may differ significantly, in incentive letters, the nature of their relationship is often situationally equal.[11. T.14 p. 28]

Based on the results of business correspondence, mutually beneficial cooperation is planned, which can bring profit to both interlocutors. If the recipient fulfills the request, business contacts between the companies will continue and expand. In the case of the prescribed action, a new situation is created.

In order to effectively communicate within the framework of request letters, it is important to correctly use expressive means of expression, which may differ in different languages.[12. T.1 p. 25]

International Enterprises Ltd
10 Park Rd
Tallinn

Republican Trade Company
17 Parma Rd
Tallinn EE0001

30 April, 1994

Dear Mr. K. Tamm

We have had difficulties with our last order which need correcting. On 15 March we ordered a BTA to use with our computer system. On 21 March we received a BTAC, but it is obviously incompatible with our system. We explained the mistake and returned the product, confident that the BTA would be delivered promptly. Yesterday, more than a month after placing our order, we received another BTAC.

I am sure you can understand our concern. How would you feel if you were in our place? We know that everyone makes mistakes, but a further delay in the implementation of our system will cause us great inconvenience. Please send us a BTA before 15 May or refund our payment of \$1,500.00.

Yours sincerely
Paul Bank
Managing Director

8 Kennedy Circle
Sydney
NSW 2010

11 November, 2015

Customer Services Manager
Evans Electrical Products
7 Swan Street
Sydney
NSW 2011

Subject: EasyIron Electric Iron (Model No. 2279)

Dear Sir or Madam:

I wish to express my dissatisfaction with the above iron, which I purchased from The Electrical Store in Newtown on 10 October, 2015. On using it for the first time, I found that the temperature control was faulty; it was not possible to set it for any temperature apart from the highest, for cotton.

When I attempted to return the iron to the store, the cashier said that the store was unable to replace it or offer me a refund but advised me that it could be sent away for repair. As I need an iron on a daily basis, and it was not clear how long a repair would take, this option was unsatisfactory. As the iron clearly does not function as it should and therefore does not comply with the legal standards of product quality, I am writing to you to ask for a full refund of the £35.99 retail price.

I look forward to hearing from you within the next two weeks.

Yours truly,

Jenny Hawkins

Picture 1 - Use of intonation and parentheses in a complaint letter

Complaints or letters of complaint contain complaints about non-compliance with any requirements, dissatisfaction with the data provided, services rendered, or products delivered on time.

The communicative purpose of complaints is to clarify incorrect information, compensate for losses, and resolve the conflict. [13. T.1 p. 28]

When business partners do not fulfill their obligations under General agreements, a problematic situation arises, which is further reflected in the business letter. In a joint conflict, it is necessary to clearly and objectively state the essence of the problem, explain all inconsistencies, and then find a common solution and encourage the addressee to perform an action that can resolve the conflict.

Dear Anna,

Please kindly answer my e-mail. Do you have any news? We require the goods by 1 July at least. The customer is very much worried about the situation.

Perhaps we could meet to discuss this – are you free next Friday at 11 am? Please let me know.

Best regards,

John Smith

Sales manager

Dear Sirs,

We have known about Rotafarm at exhibition in Milan, and we would very much appreciate if you will send us more detailed description of your production. We would like to know the discounts that you provide.

Our company specializes in distributing medicine in Moscow. For your information we may add that our company was established five years ago. If your goods meet our requirements, and we receive a favourable offer, we will be able to represent your production in Russia.

We are looking forward to your reply.

Yours faithfully,

Picture 2 - The use of intonation and brackets in the traditional letter (on the left) and email (right)

The analysis in this paper is based in General on examples of traditional letters. However, we cannot fail to mention the influence of electronic communication. According to A.O.Stebletsova, there is a linguistic-stylistic continuity between traditional and electronic letters, the latter of which differ in a certain originality. Internet communication is very popular in the modern world, because electronic applications allow you to exchange information in the shortest possible time. Many people switch to e-mail, while forgetting about some traditions of written communication and the General distance between business partners. Undoubtedly, electronic resources provide more opportunities for communication, while influencing traditional business correspondence. Electronic communication expands the circle of communication, so the correspondence goes beyond the traditional correspondence and acquires the features of a polylogue.

Due to the rapid spread of e-mail, some examples of email correspondence should be included in the analysis.

On the one hand, in the above example of an email in English, there are features of the official business style: the label formulas of politeness and the adverbs 'kindly' and 'please' are used. However, at the syntax level, simple sentences and amplifying 'very much' particles predominate, which reflect the author's self-expression, increase the actual function of correspondence, and improve communication. [14. T.1 p. 185]

This means that clear style boundaries no longer exist.

The wide and active spread of the globalization process was the result of the desire of the international community to unite, which led to the urgent need to create a universal language of peace, communication and interaction. Currently, the status of lingua franca in the international arena belongs to the English language. Today, English is the native language of 400 million people, and it also occupies a leading position in the ranking of countries where it is used on an unofficial basis, for example, for educational purposes.

In this regard, the phenomenon of language interference in the context of communication in English is being actively discussed today, since it has become the language of all spheres of life, including the language of international education. The phenomenon of language interference is a process, on the one hand, based on the linguistic and psychosocial aspects of interaction between representatives of different language groups. On the other hand, this process is inevitable for people who study foreign languages, especially those who belong to different language groups or families. As a result of such language contacts, due to the globalization of the world community, and there was a variation in the pronunciation of the English language.

In the modern world, business correspondence reaches a new level. Continuous correspondence brings companies from different countries closer together and contributes to the conclusion of contracts, which subsequently stimulates economic growth in the world. This means that business correspondence is one of the most effective and widespread channels of communication between business partners, despite the transition of correspondence to electronic applications.

Due to the high prevalence of correspondence, participants in the business sphere face certain conditions of behavior, as well as requirements to comply with the etiquette of business communication, which is necessary for the registration of business correspondence. The future course of communication depends on the ability to correctly and clearly formulate ideas and on the skills of business etiquette. Many companies and institutions use business letters to communicate with each other and with the outside world in General. In business correspondence, companies exchange profitable information, clarify relations, make claims to each other, make suggestions on any issues.[15. T.1 p. 37]

The specific content of emails is reflected in the language features. Although the language of each letter is different, since it contains different business situations and features of a particular author, there are common design and writing criteria for all business letters. In the business sphere, it is necessary to present the content of the letter logically. State standards for written correspondence prescribe requirements for clear presentation of information, which subsequently ensures an objective understanding of the business document on the part of the addressee. Moreover, written business communication is carried out within groups of business partners and organizations, so it is important to clearly and objectively reflect the content of the message.

Business documents are strictly regulated in accordance with state and international standards and have legal force. At the same time, business communication letters can be considered as an expression of communicative goals and intentions that provide information links and stimulate business interaction. Contacting a specific partner requires compliance with a specific communication situation. The communicative task of a business letter creates a certain context for research, namely a discursive approach. The description of the text as the main unit of communication prescribes the basis for discourse analysis, in which discourse is defined in the dictionary of N. D. Arutyunov as a specific work linked to a specific event

[1]. It is determined by extralinguistic factors of impact pragmatics and internal psychology of the author of the work.

From this point of view, it is important to consider the texts of business letters from the point of view of motivational and expressive aspects of the addressee's written speech activity. The intentional content of the letter reflects the individual characteristics of the author, thanks to which the addressee expresses his attitude to the described situation. This encourages the author to adhere to the perlocative effect, which increases the effectiveness and efficiency of business communication.

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